

Saint Catherine's Monastery

Secondary source

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** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Religious Group, Monastery, Egypt, Early Christian Monasticism in Egypt, Religious Place

Saint Catherine's Monastery (official name: Sacred Autonomous Royal Monastery of Saint Katherine of the Holy and God-Trodden Mount Sinai) is believed to be the oldest continuously inhabited Christian monastery in the world. Located in Egypt at the foot of Mount Sinai, it was commissioned by the Emperor Justinian I in 565 C.E. In fact, there are two inscriptions from the time of the monastery's founding that survive. One says "For the salvation of our most august emperor Justinian." The other says, "For the memory and repose of our departed empress Theodora." The monastery is said to have been built around the original burning bush encountered by Moses. It also houses a large collection of early Christian icons and one of the oldest continuously functioning libraries in world. The monastery complex, surrounded by thick, granite walls, consists of a main church surrounded by nine smaller chapels, with monks' quarters along parts of the surrounding walls. It has been occupied continuously by monks since the 6th century. In the Middle Ages, Crusaders briefly visited the monastery as a site of pilgrimage, and inscriptions in Frankish in the refectory built by the Crusaders still survive. After the Ottoman conquest of Egypt in 1517, the monastery fell under the protection of Sultan Selim I. Today, it is a fully functioning monastery within the Orthodox Church. Part of the monks' duty is to protect the monastery and surrounding holy sites for the sake of pilgrims.

Date Range: 565 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Mount Sinai, Monastery of St. Catherine

Region tags: Egypt, Egyptian Desert

The Monastery of St. Catherine at Mount Sinai, where John of the Ladder composed the "Ladder of the Divine Ascent".

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Leroy, Jules. *Monks and Monasteries of the Near East*. London: G. G. Harrap, 1963.
- Source 2: Menze, Volker-Lorenz. *Justinian and the Making of the Syrian Orthodox Church*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008.
- Source 3: Saad El Din, Mursi., Ayman. Taher, and Luciano. Romano. *Sinai: the Site & the History: Essays /*. New York: New York University Press, 1998.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.sinaimonastery.com/index.php/en/>
- Source 1 Description: The official website of St. Catherine's Monastery
- Source 2 URL: <http://campus.belmont.edu/honors/Sinailcons/Sinailcons.html>
- Source 2 Description: Online images of many of the early icons found at St. Catherine's Monastery
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MZ3dFABGySg>
- Source 3 Description: Short video about the monastery

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: This short article speaks about the archeological findings:

<https://stcatherines.mused.org/en/stories/46/the-monastery-of-sinai-and-the-living-quarters-of-its-roman-guardians>

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2000-2010

Notes: Conducted by the Hellenic Archaeological Mission at South Sinai.

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: The Hellenic Archaeological Mission at South Sinai.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: The monastery is at the foot of Mt. Sinai in the Egyptian desert.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: The monastery is situated in a relatively isolated part of the Sinai desert. There is now, however, a small town called St. Catherine built near the monastery.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Again, the small town of St. Catherine is situated near the monastery.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Travelers can go to either the town of Sharm El-Sheikh or Dahab, both about 6.5 miles from the monastery. In the ancient world, the journey would have been far from safe, surrounded as the monastery was by miles and miles of empty desert.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: Again, there are now two resort towns about 6.5 miles from the monastery. One can fly to one of those towns and then either drive or hike to the monastery. Obviously, in its original 6th century context, this was not the case.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Mount Sinai which may or may not be the mountain referenced in the Mosaic story.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery is surrounded by walls. The main church, the Church of St. Catherine, was built in the 6th century and most of its original structure still survives, although a belfry was added in 1871. An older church, the Church of St. Helena, was incorporated into the main church. There are 12 other chapels within the monastery's walls. There is also an oblong Old Refectory with many carvings, including some symbols of Crusader knights. Another building houses a gallery of ancient icons, while the library contains over 4,500 manuscripts. Finally, there are monks' dwellings situated along the walls and several active wells.

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Notes: The entire monastery complex is part of one unit.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: Monks are supposed to pray continuously, both in a communal sense at scheduled daily times and on their own.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: Monasteries were built to last through generations, although few if any have survived as long as St. Catherine's.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: While the original monastery was built in the 6th century and many structures

survive from this era, many features have been added or repaired since then. For example, a north wing was built as a library in 1951, the Old Refectory goes back to the 15th century, and the belfry was added in 1871.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

↳ In antiquity
– Periodically

↳ In modernity
– Renaissance
– Post-Renaissance

Notes: These consist of both repairs and new constructions as listed above.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: To the Christian god.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Notes: The Trinity is invoked but trinitarian theology states that Father, Son, and Holy Spirit are actually one god.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:
– No

Notes: Jesus of Nazareth is said to have been the god-man, fully human and fully divine.

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: However, sainted monks are venerated, and these could be considered "ancestors" of current monks.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: As mentioned earlier, the monastery was commissioned and built by the Byzantine Emperor Justinian I, who reigned from 527 to 565.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The monastery may have been built by 6th century monks, but it's sophisticated architecture would seem to demand highly skilled professional architects and builders.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Notes: Significantly, though, the original chapel around which the monastery would be built was said to have been built around the original burning bush from which Yahweh spoke to Moses in Exodus 3.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Notes: Again, the burning bush provided inspiration for the original chapel.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Justinian was a Christian Byzantine emperor.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: While this was not the principal purpose for its construction, its library became the repository for a huge number of rare ancient manuscripts including the Codex Sinaiticus. There are manuscripts in many ancient languages including Greek, Palestinian Aramaic, Syriac, Georgian, Arabic, Ethiopic/Ge'ez, Latin, Armenian, Church Slavonic, and Caucasian Albanian, and Coptic books.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The entire monastery complex is built. at the foot of Mount Sinai.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– No

Notes: It is apparently cedar wood from Lebanon.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

Notes: The desert environment doesn't provide heavy wood like cedar.

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

Notes: The vast majority of the monastery walls and buildings are made of granite blocks.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: For example, the wooden doors of the main church contain carved reliefs of animals, plants, and an inscription.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Paintings of Christ and angels are present.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Biblical figures and other saints are depicted.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Principally on the doors of the main church.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

Notes: In many paintings, but not in the reliefs.

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Notes: Principally in the main church and the Old Refectory.

↳ Type
–Secco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

Notes: Christ is depicted, however.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Biblical stories are depicted.

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There is one mosaic cross decorating the apse of the Chapel of the Burning Bush.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– No

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: At least one of them. The Old Refectory has stone carvings with Frankish inscriptions.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: This includes paintings of Christ, angels, and saints (who were, of course, human but have been elevated to a higher supernatural status since their deaths.)

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: There are many crosses depicted throughout the complex.

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Again, acknowledging that saints are human beings who are glorified after death, there is an iconostasis in the main church depicting many saints.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Many miracle stories are depicted in the main church and the Old Refectory.

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: However, the website of the monastery states that "in the garden," just outside the monastery walls "is the small cemetery with the Chapel of St. Tryphon and the Charnel House. The scantiness of earth does not permit permanent graves, so the monks buried in the cemetery are later exhumed and their bones placed in the ossuary."

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Notes: Not the monastery as a whole, but as stated above, bodies are buried and then later exhumed and the bones taken to an ossuary.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the

tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: A bit of a complicated theological question. Since this monastery is of the Orthodox variety, the answer could be that "God is everywhere" in the sense of having no physical location. However, there are many references to God in heaven and to Christ ascending,

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

Notes: The Christ is often referred to as a king.

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: There are no references I could find in which god communicated directly with someone at the monastery. However, since monks spend a great deal of time in prayer and meditation, it seems possible.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Notes: With the qualification that saints are said to help those in need who communicate with them.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Notes: As usual in Christian monasteries, there are many references to angels but none explicitly detailing how they are present.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Monks follow a strict schedule as well as multiple ethical precepts.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

Notes: The only "offerings" expected are frequent prayers.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Notes: Total celibacy is required of all monks.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: The monks follow a strict regimen involving scheduled prayers throughout the day.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

Notes: This is especially true of the church and chapels which are holy places.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Honoring oaths would certainly fall under the banner of honesty which is required, especially with one's superior.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Visitors to the monastery are allowed to pray in the church or chapels at designated times.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably, since this is an Orthodox monastery, visitors may communicate with saints as well.

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

Notes: Prayer services are scheduled throughout each day and are absolutely mandatory.

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: It can be assumed that it is required from a historical perspective. However, I haven't

found any list of specific tasks required of the monks.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: There have been many repairs/reconstructions since the monastery was built. I assume the monks do those when possible.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– I don't know

Notes: Again, I assume the monks do whatever tasks they can in repair and maintenance and hire out for tasks that require more skills or expertise.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: From the monastery website: "For the Sinaite fathers, all visitors are dealt with as pilgrims from whom their respect towards the sanctity of the site, the Sinai pilgrimage sites, and their daily programme of prayer is considered as a given fact. It is considered wise policy to avoid visiting the Monastery on its official feastdays, as it is closed to the general public."

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– I don't know

Notes: Pilgrims to sites such as this monastery are often in some kind of distress and praying for help. However, this monastery is not associated with any particular life events.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Notes: There are saints' feasts, but these are solemn celebrations of the life of particular saints, not bacchanals.

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: There is no evidence of this, but historically people who needed healing visited monasteries, believing that monks could intercede for them with the deity. It seems likely that this still happens at St. Catherine's.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Communal prayer is a daily occurrence.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Monks pray privately and have private altars in their cells.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: 36 monks live at the monastery and all are required to participate in communal prayers.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Five times a day.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– I don't know

Notes: In a sense, communal prayer rituals are an orthodoxy check, as well as the confession mandated for each monk on a regular basis.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– Yes
Notes: Daily rituals are a constant orthopraxy test.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– No
Notes: While wine is used for the Eucharist, intoxicants in general are forbidden.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time
– Yes
Notes: Monks are all religious specialists and they all live in the monastery and care for it full time.

↳ Present part time
– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
– Yes
Notes: This monastery is exclusively for male monks.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
– No
Notes: This is a Greek Orthodox monastery, but one is not required to be ethnically Greek to be a monk there.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

Notes: Becoming a monk is a commitment for life.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Monks live at the monastery full time so they have living quarters, known as "cells."

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Novice monks receive training in the practices and procedures of monasticism.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: While this is a technically a monastery of the Greek Orthodox Church, the monastery is Autocephalous, meaning that it is fully responsible for itself and not beholden to other church authorities.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Notes: According to St. Catherine's Monastery website, the monastery "is characterized by the unique privilege in Orthodox Christianity of being governed administratively by its abbot who is the same person as the Archbishop of Sinai and of being "unsubdued, immune, untrampled by

anyone, and totally free from all and everyone. Furthermore, it is Autocephalous,"as it is not subject to any Patriarch or Synod." In addition, "it is democratically governed by its Abbot and Archbishop of Sinai, Pharan, and Raitho, the Holy Council of the Fathers, as well as by the assembly of the entire brotherhood which is convened from time to time."

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: However, the Codex Sinaiticus, one of the earliest complete manuscripts of the Bible, was found here in the monastery library.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Saint Catherine's Monastery, Forsyth, G. H. , and K. Weitzmann. The Monastery of Saint Catherine at Mount Sinai - the Church and Fortress of Justinian. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1973.

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